
EMPLOYEE RETENTION TECHNIQUES AND PERFORMANCE OF FAMILY-OWNED BUSINESSES IN ENUGU METROPOLIS, ENUGU, NIGERIA.

¹Ojide Chukwemeka Gabriel, ²Prof. T.O Enudu, ³Dr. OKAFOR Ozoemena Christian and ⁴Okafor Juliana Nkechi

^{1,2,4}Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT

³Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Esut)

Email: emekaojidegabriel@gmail.com/ okey.enudu@esut.edu.ng/ peter.ozoemena@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14794208>

ABSTRACT: The study focused on employee retention techniques and performance of family-owned businesses in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were to determine the nature of the relationship between training and development opportunities and sales growth, as well as, ascertain the nature of the relationship between good pay package and profit of family-owned businesses in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. The study had a population of 1,850 owners of family-owned businesses in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. A sample-size of 329 owners of family-owned businesses studied was determined through Taro Yamane's formula. Instruments used for data collection were primarily, the questionnaire and interviews. A total of 329 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, while 309 copies were properly filled/returned, leaving 20 copies not properly filled. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Two hypotheses were tested and analyzed, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple linear regression tool. The findings indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between training and development opportunities and sales growth of family-owned businesses in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .907$; $F = 198.730$; $t = 14.097$; $p < 0.05$). There was also a significant positive relationship between good pay package and profit of family-owned businesses in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .901$, $p < .05$). The study concluded that both training and development opportunities and good pay package had significant positive relationship with sales growth and profit of family-owned businesses, respectively in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommended among other things, that owners of family-owned businesses be encouraged to set up training and development opportunities programs that would improve skills and enhance career growth opportunities of the employees. Similarly, owners of family-owned businesses were equally encouraged to use good pay package as a motivation tool to enhance job satisfaction and commitment that would improve performance, to retain their talented employees.

Keywords: Employee retention, Family-owned businesses, Training and development, good pay package, Sales growth

INTRODUCTION

Today's Business environment considers the role of human resource as a strategic partner, rather than supporting administrative tasks because the greatest asset of an organization are its people. Talent management is of core to the vitality of the business to meet and exceed current, as well as future business strategies and goals (Gupta, *et al*, 2011). Employees are important resources to any organization. Based on their critical character, they can be termed the life blood of an organization.

Employee retention is a global concern and employers in every industry are suffering due to high voluntary employee turnover. According to Bake (2019), dissatisfied employees will start looking for other jobs even in an uncertain economy, and could be challenging to retain these employees. Banerjee (2019) explained that lack of effective employee strategies might impact customer satisfaction, sales volume, productivity, and

profitability. Human resources strategies not focusing on employee engagement and a healthy working environment may result in a higher voluntary turnover rate.

Cui, *et al* (2018) posit that part of the retention strategy should involve employees in the decision-making process, which develops management trust within the employees. Employee retention strategies, therefore is a plan an organization has put in place to create a conducive environment that meet the needs of the employees to hold onto their top talents in the management (Ecsafy and Oraby, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Talent retention and acquisition are bigger priorities than ever for many companies especially those focused on growth. Since it is likely that these challenges will persist, businesses will need an employee-centric strategy that is built on trust and definitive action to win the war for talent. Voluntary turnover impacts business profitability due to additional recruitment, training, and overtime expenses, as well as risk of low productivity levels of newly hired employees. This can negatively affect the overall performance of an organization by increasing the cost of operations, and of course reducing profits. When there is employee retention in place, turnover intentions become low because there is provision for career opportunities, positive work environment, good work-life balance, organizational justice, good organizational image, opportunities for growth and development, good pay package, job security, job enrichment, flexible tasks, job enlargement, etc.

However, when there is lack of employee retention, the organization is likely to experience high turnover intentions because there is no provision for career opportunities, poor work-life balance, presence of organizational injustices, poor pay package, job insecurity, lack of training and development, lack of job enrichment, absence of job enlargement and so on. Thus, lack of these work-place incentives are the reasons why employees leave their organizations in search of other organizations that can offer better incentives. It is based on these challenges problems that informed the researcher's choice to embark on this study to profer solutions to the problems highlighted.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study focused on employee retention techniques and performance of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Determine the nature of the relationship between training and development opportunities and sales growth of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the extent of the relationship to which good pay package influences the profit of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Employee

An employee refers to an individual who works for an organization in exchange for compensation. Employees are crucial to the success of family-owned businesses, as their skills, commitment, and productivity directly impact overall performance of an organization.

Retention

The term "retention" refers to the ability of an organization to keep its employees over time. When retention rate is high, it arises from a positive work environment and can enhance organizational stability, particularly in family-owned businesses. Conversely, if the retention rate is low, which arises from poor and negative work environment, thus resulting in organizational instability of family businesses.

Technique

Technique can be described as a method or strategy employed to achieve a specific goal or objective. In relation to this study, techniques are the specific approaches taken by businesses to ensure that employees remain satisfied and engaged in their roles.

Employee Retention

Employee retention refers to employees staying with an organization for an extended period because of the measures that the organization has put in place. Singh (2019) noted that employee retention refers to keeping the employees of an organization working willingly with their employer for a longer time because of different measures being implemented by the employer.

Employee Retention Technique

Employee retention techniques are those specific methods or practices implemented by an organization to enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty. It includes competitive compensation packages, career development opportunities and a positive organizational culture.

Proxies of Employee Retention Technique

Proxies of employee retention techniques are those indirect measures or indicators that can be used to assess the effectiveness of employee retention techniques. In the context of employee retention, it may include employee engagement scores, turnover rates, job satisfaction surveys, and employee referrals.

Components of Employee Retention Techniques

The components of employee retention techniques are those key elements that contribute to successful retention strategies, examples include, competitive salaries and attractive benefits, career development opportunities, positive and supportive workplace culture, acknowledgement of employee contributions and achievements, and a healthy work-life balance.

Components of Employee Retention Techniques that formed part of the Objectives of the Study

The components of employee retention techniques that formed part of the objective of this study include training and development opportunities, as well as, good pay package.

Training and Development Opportunities:

- Promoting skill development programs such as workshops, seminars and courses aimed at enhancing employee skills.
- Putting in place career advancement plans through clear pathways for promotions and career growth.
- Encouraging mentorship programs by pairing less experienced employees with seasoned professionals for guidance.

Good Pay Package

A good pay package simply refers to a comprehensive remuneration structure that includes base salary, bonuses, benefits and non-monetary incentives designed to attract, motivate and retain employees. In the context of family-owned businesses, a well-structured pay package can significantly influence employee satisfaction and retention.

Benefits are increasingly important to employees, because they contribute to overall job satisfaction and work-life balance (Deloitte, 2021).

Performance

Performance simply refers to how effectively an individual or organization achieves its goals. Performance can be measured through such indicators as, productivity, profitability, and customer satisfaction.

Family-Owned Business

Family businesses (FBs) constitute the predominant form of ownership in current markets (e.g., Carney, Van Essen, Gedajlovic & Heugens, 2015). Frey (2011) noted that a family-owned business is a form of business in which a family is in control of shares, daily operations, mission and strategy. To Leach et al (1990), it is a business where a single family effectively controls the firm through the ownership of greater than 50% of the voting shares, and a significant portion of the firm's senior management team is drawn from the same family.

Performance Indicators of Family-Owned Businesses

The performance indicators of family-owned businesses include:

- Financial performance, which includes profit margins, revenue growth and return on investment (ROI).
- Operational performance, which includes efficiency ratios, as well as customer retention rates.
- Employee performance, which includes employee turnover rates and employee satisfaction scores.
- Market performance, which includes market share, as well as brand reputation and loyalty.

Performance Indicators of Family-Business that formed part of the Objectives of the Study

- Sales growth: This involves measuring the increase in sales as an indicator of the effectiveness of training and development.
- Profit margins: Involves evaluating how a good pay package impacts overall profitability.

Sales Growth

Sales growth refers to the increase in a company’s sales over a specific period, measured in terms of revenue or units sold. In the context of family-owned businesses, sales growth is not only a key performance indicator, but also influences the sustainability and legacy of family businesses. Investing in employee training, enhances sales team effectiveness. Family businesses invest in digital marketing, social media, and online sales channels can reach broader audiences, increasing their sales potential (Perez et al., 2020).

Profit

Profit is the financial gain obtained when the revenue from business activities exceeds the costs and expenses associated with those activities. Profit is not only a measure of financial success, but plays a critical role in sustainability, growth, and long-term legacy of family-owned businesses.

Conceptual Framework

In this study, the conceptual framework considers factors such as the effectiveness of training and development programs, as well as, the alignment of good pay package with employee needs in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Fig 2.1 Conceptual model of the study.

Source: Authorities that contributed to the components and performance indicators of this study.

Theoretical Review

This study was anchored on Social Exchange theory. The theory propounded by early scholars like George Homans (1961) Peter Blau (1964), John Thibaut and Harold Kelly (1959) posit that relationships are based on reciprocal exchanges. It states that social behavior is the result of an exchange process, where individuals seek to maximize their rewards and minimize their costs. The Social Exchange theorists argue that employees leave when there is a breach in the terms of exchange. These are either explicit or implicit and are agreed upon by the employer and the employee. The attributes of goods exchanged can be physical (such as money for service) or quality attributes like trust, loyalty, commitment, etc.

This employee retention theory also focuses on how strong social ties within an organization encourages people to stay longer and grants more satisfied employees. Thus, a simple way to avoid undesired turnover in such cases would be to activate management to respect and uphold rules that are agreed upon.

Empirical Review

Onumoh, Halima and Bello (2022) did a study on impact of rewards on employee performance of SMEs in Gusau metropolis of Zamfara state, Nigeria. Three were research hypotheses. The study uses quantitative data collection technique. The study indicated that dependent and independent variables of the research were strongly and positively correlated with each other.

Kalapapa (2016) examine the impact of training and development on employee performance, while the specific objectives are to identify training and development methods; examine the relationship between training and development on employee performance; determine the effect of training and development on employee performance; and to determine factors affecting employee performance. The study reviewed the concept of training, development as well as training and development. The study furthermore analysed training and development methods under on-the-job and off-the-job training such as job rotation, coaching/mentoring, orientation, conferences, role playing, and formal training courses/development programmes.

Maryam, Hadiza Saiduand and Cross (2023) did a study on effect of compensation (measured by financial and non-financial compensation) on employees' job performance at Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Kano State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design. The study found that financial compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee job performance, while non-financial compensation has a positive but insignificant effect on employee job, performance of DMBs in Kano State, Nigeria.

Alabi *et al.*, (2022) examined the relationship between non-monetary rewards and employee performance in money deposit banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study adopted a cross-sectional design. The study's population comprised five (5) deposit money banks licensed by the Central Bank of Nigeria. The findings reveal that all the dimensions of non-financial reward significantly affect employee performance among selected financial institutions at a 0.05 level of significance.

Gap in Empirical Literature

The existing literature lacks a comprehensive understanding of the specific mechanisms through which training and development opportunities and good pay package influence employee retention of family businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. While previous research has established a general association between retention techniques and training and development opportunities, as well as, good pay package, there is a dearth

of studies, focusing specifically on employee retention of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. Furthermore, the idea that both training and development and good pay package had significant relationship with employee retention remains underexplored within the family-owned businesses.

METHODOLOGY

Given the nature of this study, a survey research design was adopted. A survey is a series of self-report measures administered either through an interview or a written questionnaire (Stangor, 2007:103). The study population of 1,850 owners of family businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria was drawn through Convenience Sampling technique, due to the accessibility of the target population. In this study, the sample-size utilized was 329 owners of family-owned businesses determined through Taro Yaman'e formula. The sampling techniques utilized in this study describe how the participants were selected and how the data were collected. In this study, the owners of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, were used as target population. The researcher adopted simple random sampling, thus ensuring that every individual has an equal chance of being chosen. The population was divided into strata and participants randomly selected from each stratum. Participants are also selected based on their availability and willingness to participate. In this study, At the inferential level of analyses, linear regression was used to test hypotheses 1, while hypotheses 2 was tested, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 5% level of significance to determine the extent of correlation between the dependent and independent variables.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H0: Training and development has no effect on sales growth of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.907 ^a	.822	.818	.44000	.451

a. Predictors: (Constant), training and development

b. Dependent Variable: Sales growth

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.475	1	38.475	198.730	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.325	43	.194		
	Total	46.800	44			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), training and development

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	.616	.114		5.393	.000
	training and development	.750	.053	.907	14.097	.000

a. Dependent Variable: performance indicators of family-owned businesses (sales growth)

$r = .907$

$r^2 = .822$

$F = 198.730$

$T = 14.097$

$DW = .451$

The regression sum of squares (38.475) is greater than the residual sum of squares (8.325) and this indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. The significance of the F value indicates that the model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. The correlation coefficient r has a value of 0.907 and this indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between training and development and sales growth of family-owned businesses. Square of the coefficient of determination, shows that 82.2% of the variation in performance family-owned businesses is explained by the model.

In the linear regression model, a low error of estimate with a value of 0.44000 is indicated. A value of 0.451 for the Durbin Watson statistics which is less than 2 indicates that there is no correlation. The training and development coefficient of 0.907 indicates a positive significance, training and with employee retention of family-owned businesses, in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria, ($r = .907; F=198.730; t 14.097; p<.05$) which is statistically significant ($t = 14.097$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted, thus training and development has significant and positive effect on sales growth of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H0: There is no relationship between good pay package and profit of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Good Pay Package	1.9778	1.17722	309
Profit of FOBs	2.1556	.90342	309

Correlations

		Good package	Pay Family Owned Businesses
Good Pay Package	Pearson Correlation	1	.901**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	309	309
Profit of family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	.901**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	309	309

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of this study include the following:

- i. Training and development had a significant and positive effect on sales growth of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. ($r = .907$; $F = 198.730$; $t = 14.097$; $p < 0.05$).
- ii. There is a significant relationship between good pay package and profit of family-owned businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. ($r = .901$, $P < .05$).

Conclusion

The study examined employee retention techniques and performance of family-owned Businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. Data collected and analyzed indicate that there is significant positive relationship between all Employee retention techniques variables and all performance indicators of family-owned business variables measured. Consequently, we therefore conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between Employee Retention techniques and Performance of family-owned Businesses in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study, recommended among other things that owners of family businesses be encouraged to set up training and development opportunities programs that will address the specific needs and career aspirations of their employees. Similarly, owners of family businesses are equally encouraged to utilize good pay package, as a motivation tool, in addition to other workplace incentives, to enhance job satisfaction and commitment, thus, enhancing retention of talented employees.

Contribution to Knowledge

Leveraging on Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, the model suggests that individuals have a hierarchy of needs ranging from basic physiological needs to self-actualization. And once the lower-level needs are satisfied, individuals seek to fulfill higher-level needs. In relation to this model, good pay package can satisfy basic and safety needs, while training and development opportunities can help fulfill esteem and self-actualization needs, thus enhancing job satisfaction and retention of talented employees.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad Z, Md Said and Abd. L (2012). The impact of training on small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) Performance, *Journal of Professional Management*, 2 (1), 9-19
- Bilan, Y., Mishchuk, H., Roshchyk, I., & Joshi, O. (2020). Hiring and retaining skilled employees in SMEs: Problems in human resource practices and links with organizational success. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(2), 780–791
- Chrisman James J, Chus, Jess. H., and Steier, L P. (2005). An Investigation of the Contribution of Management Development to Small form Performance, *Journal of Small Business Management*, United States. 1(11), 56-78
- Chua, J. H., Chrisman, J. J., & Sharma, P. (1999). Defining the family business by behavior. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 23(4), 19–39
- Das, L. B., & Baruah, M. (2013). Employee retention: A review of literature. *IOSR Journal of Business Management*, 14 (2), 08-16.
- Elsafty, A., & Oraby, M. (2022). The impact of training on employee retention: empirical research on the private sector in Egypt. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 17(5), 58–74
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2021). MSME survey report. National Bureau of Statistics. https://smedan.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2021-MSME-Survey-Report_1.pdf
- Goel, Swati, Caupta, Manish, and Rastogi, Rekesh (2020). Impact of employee recognition on employee performance: a comparative study of private and public sector, *Journal of Management Research*, India. 1(2), 11-23
- Gustave M.K and Shepherd D (2022) Rewards and innovation performance in manufacturing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1737
- Iqbal, S., Yun, T. H., & Akhtar, S. (2019). Organizational culture and employee retention at SMEs in Pakistan; An investigation of mediating role of quality of work life. *International Journal of Research*, 6(10), 647–657
- Kalapapa B (2016) Impact of training and development on employee performance, *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 6(3) 43-56
- Kiruthiga, V. & Magesh, R. (2014). Brunt of employee retention strategies on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 2(2), 394-398.

- Kurdi, B., Alshurideh, M., & Al afaishat, T. (2020). Employee retention and organizational performance: Evidence from banking industry. *Management Science Letters*, 10(16), 3981
- Moncarz, E. S., Zhao, J., & Kay, S. (2009). Workplace injuries and the provision of post-injury employer accommodations and benefits. *Journal of safety Research*, 40(3), 201 – 208.
- Nguyen, Tui Thanh Thay, Pahm, Van Hien, and Trinh, Van Quyet (2016). *The effects of non-monetary rewards on the satisfaction and employee retention: A survey Research of Logistics Enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam*, University of Economics He Chi Minh City,
- Victnon. Aronoff Craig E., and Ward, John L. (1995). *Creating a culture of recognition*”, AMACOM (American Management Association), United States.
- Oganezi, B .U.and Lozie, D (2017). Employee retention strategy and performance of commercial banks in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, *Funai Journal of Accounting, Federal University Business and Finance (Fujabf) Ndufu-Alike Ikwo Ebonyi State Nigeria* 1(1) 279-287
- Onumoh A, Halima A and Bello U (2022) Impact of financial reward on employees’ performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) In Gusau Metropolis of Zamfara State, Nigeria, *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)* 4(8),8-23
- Patrick,W.,& Newlin, M. (2018). Implementing a total reward strategy in selected South African municipal organizations. *South African Journal of Human Resource Management*, 16(1), 1-9
- Ranganathan, A. (2018). Train them to retain them: Work readiness and the retention of first-time women workers in India. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 63(4), 879-909
- Ro, H., & Lee, J. (2017). Call center employees’ intent to quit: examination of job engagement and role clarity. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 18(4), 531-543
- Simon, H. A. (1960). *The new science of management decisions*. New York: Harper and Row
- Singh, D. (2019). A literature review on employee retention with focus on recent trends. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 6(1), 425–431
- Thibault, L., Schweyer, A., & Whillans, A. (2017). Winning the war for talent: Modern motivational methods for attracting and retaining employees. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 49(4), 230-246
- Yayi, F.I. O. (2002). Decision-making in underdeveloped organizations: An exploratory investigation. *Nigeria Journal of Business Administration*. 4(1), 45-49

Zaharee, M., Lipkie, T., Mehlman, S. K., & Neylon, S. K. (2018). Recruitment and retention of early-career technical talent: What young employees want from employers. *Research Technology Management*, 61(5), 51-61

Bennett, R. (2017). Pay and performance. The Importance of Employee Motivation. *Business Horizons*, 60(2), 173-183.

Deloitte, A (2021). *Global human capital trends: The Social Enterprise in a World Disrupted*.

Perez, S., et al., (2020). E-commerce and family business: a review and research agenda. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 10(1), 32-48.

Garcia-Castro, R., & Francoeur, C. (2016). The impact of corporate social responsibility on profitability: the role of governance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 134(1), 1-24.